

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEMS. REFRACTOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS OF ALKALI SULPHATES DISSOLVED IN FUSED BORAX GLASS

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The values of the mole refraction (R) of solutions of highly purified samples of Li_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 in fused glass in different concentrations have been compared to those of the pure crystal and of the aqueous solution at infinite dilution. The values exhibit considerable departure, attributable to the strong deformation which these salts suffer in solid solution in glass medium. The slope of the R - c curve is positive in every case (*cf.* the works of Fajans' school) implying meagre dissociation of the salt in the glass medium. The densities of the samples exhibit some peculiarities which can be explained by the recent views about the structure of glasses as proposed by Warren and Zachariasen.

The present work is an extension of the work done by one of us (S. K. M.) on the study of deformation of polar crystals dissolved in glass (Wulff and Majumdar, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B, 31, 319; Majumdar and Sarma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 241; Majumdar and Saha, *ibid.*, 1945, 22, 147; Majumdar and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1946, 23, 149). The object of the work is to study the deformability of alkali sulphates (Li_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4) dissolved in fused borax glass as shown by the mole-refraction values.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Samples.—Lithium sulphate was prepared by dissolving pure lithium carbonate in just sufficient sulphuric acid, boiling off the dissolved carbon dioxide and crystallising in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. The salt was purified by twice recrystallising in a similar way. Merck's "guaranteed reagent" variety of the other salts were dissolved in conductivity water and twice recrystallised.

The samples were heated in a hot air-oven until constant weights were obtained. The samples of the glasses were obtained in the manner described in a previous communication (Majumdar and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*).

Analysis of the Samples.—A weighed amount of the glass was dissolved in hot water and treated with a slight excess of barium chloride solution in presence of a fairly large excess of HCl. Under these conditions no barium borate was precipitated, as was verified later by testing the precipitated BaSO_4 for boric acid. A check experiment was made by estimating the total sodium (in the case of Na_2SO_4 - $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) in the glass samples. A definite weight of the sample was taken in a weighed platinum crucible, treated with a mixture of pure HF and H_2SO_4 and repeatedly evaporated to dryness, until a constant weight was obtained. Usually the Na_2SO_4 , calculated in

this way (after allowing for sodium in $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) tallied with the sodium sulphate calculated from BaSO_4 . In this way the concentration of the alkali sulphate in the glass was calculated.

Density determination.—The densities of the samples were determined by a floatation method followed in a previous communication (Majumdar and Sarma, *loc. cit.*). Acetylene tetrabromide and purified toluene were the liquids used in the mixture. The usual precautions were taken regarding pycnometer, etc., and the density was determined in a transparent thermostat maintained at $35^\circ (\pm 0.05)$.

Refractive Index determination.—The refractive index of the samples was determined in D-light from an Osram Sodium lamp by the Becke method backed by a Pulfrich refractometer as described in the previous paper. The refractive index of the samples, strictly speaking, should be determined (calculated from a dispersion formula) for infinitely long wave-length in order to fit in with the theoretical considerations. But for comparative purposes, the values for a particular wave-length in the visible as with the D-light may be taken without serious error. No claim is, however, made for the accuracy of the individual values beyond the third decimal place.

In the following tables the values of density and refractive index corresponding to different compositions of the various salts are recorded.

TABLE I

Li_2SO_4		Li_2SO_4 — $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ system	
%	cg/1000g.	Density.	n _D .
5.42	0.988	2.3488	1.5044
8.52	1.546	2.3468	1.4954
11.45	2.083	2.3444	1.4950
13.23	2.407	2.3430	1.4924
14.60	2.637	2.3401	1.4904

TABLE II

Na_2SO_4		Na_2SO_4 — $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ system	
%	cg/1000g.	Density.	n _D .
5.87	0.8263	2.3719	1.5091
10.04	1.414	2.3821	1.5048
14.46	2.0245	2.3951	1.5007
18.13	2.5525	2.4042	1.4975
19.83	2.782	2.4072	1.4982

TABLE III

K_2SO_4		K_2SO_4 — $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ system	
%	cg/1000g.	Density.	n _D .
5.94	0.8181	2.3695	1.5109
11.16	1.2810	2.3998	1.5076
17.64	2.0245	2.4167	1.5086
19.50	2.2380	2.4276	1.5029
21.56	2.4745	2.4337	1.5018

DISCUSSION

If n be the refractive index and d , the density of a substance, then the specific refraction, r may be calculated according to the Lorenz-Lorentz formula,

$$r = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{d}$$

If the additivity formula holds good in the glass systems studied and if p be the percentage of the alkali sulphate and $(100-p)$ that of $\frac{1}{g}$ the borax, then we have

$$r = p.r_1 + (100 - p).r_2,$$

where r_1 and r_2 are the specific refractions of the alkali sulphate and borax glass respectively. If we make the justifiable assumption that the refraction of the solvent medium remains unaltered, then we can calculate the specific refraction of the dissolved sulphate for different concentrations. The mole-refraction will be obtained by multiplying this value by the molecular weight.

In the following tables, the values of mole-refraction of the different alkali sulphates are recorded for different concentrations and compared with the values for the pure crystal and in aqueous solution at infinite dilution.

TABLE IV

System: Li_2SO_4 -borax glass

Li_2SO_4	r (mix) obs.	$r\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4$ (calc.)	$R\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4$ (calc.)	R_{sol}	R_{cryst}
5.42%	0.1261	0.0946	10.406	14.18	13.75*
8.52	0.1251	0.0948	10.426		
11.45	0.1243	0.09659*	10.920	(Coffeken, <i>loc cit.</i>)	
13.23	0.1239	0.0973	10.704		
14.50	0.1236	0.0984	10.82		

TABLE V

System: Na_2SO_4 -borax glass

Na_2SO_4	r mix(obs)	$r\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ (calc.)	$R\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ (calc.)	R_{sol}	R_{cryst}
5.869%	0.1259	0.0932	12.240	15.24	14.97*
10.04	0.1244	0.0938	13.588	(Wulff & Schaller,	
14.45	0.1228	0.0931	13.225	<i>Z. Krist.</i> , 1934,	
18.13	0.1218	0.0941	13.370	87 A, 60)	
19.83	0.1214	0.0948	13.460		

TABLE VI

System: K_2SO_4 -borax glass

K_2SO_4	r mix(obs)	$r\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$ (calc.)	$R\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$ (calc.)	R_{sol}	R_{cryst}
5.94%	0.1263	0.1015	17.69	19.30	19.07*
11.16	0.1241	0.0940	16.38	(Wulff & Heigl,	
17.64	0.1225	0.0969	16.89	<i>Z. Krist.</i> ,	
19.50	0.1217	0.0961	16.74	1931, 77, 111)	
21.56	0.1211	0.0984	16.80		

*These values represent the mean of those along different optical axes.

In the above calculations, the values for borax glass are taken as given below (Wulff and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*).

Borax glass	Density.	n_D	sp ref. (r_s)
	2.5560	1.6148	0.1278

It is apparent from the results that in the cases of the three alkali sulphates investigated, the mole-refraction of the dissolved salt is markedly less than their values either in the pure crystal or in aqueous solution at infinite dilution. Secondly, the mole refraction-concentration curve in every case shows a positive slope. For lithium sulphate, the values of R in the crystal and at infinite dilution are respectively 13.75 and 14.16 c. c., while an increase of salt concentration from 0.99 to 2.64 g. equiv./1000g. borax causes the value to increase from 10.40 to 10.77. The same behaviour is shown more or less by the other two sulphates, namely sodium and potassium sulphates. The difference ΔR ($-R_{\text{cryst}} - R_{\text{glass}}$) is most pronounced in the case of lithium sulphate which is to be expected from the Fajans deformation theory.

The mutual interaction of ions in an ionic crystal is rather complicated. The resultant effect can be resolved into four individual interactions, two of which cause an increase and the remaining two a decrease in the refraction. Briefly it may be stated as follows :

Interaction of cation on anion	...	Decrease in refraction	...	(i)
" anion on cation	...	Increase " "	...	(ii)
" cation on solvent	...	Decrease " "	...	(iii)
" anion on solvent	...	Increase " "	...	(iv)

In many cases where the cation is small or highly charged, effects (i) and (iii) preponderate over (ii) and (iv). Such for example are the cases of salts like LiCl, NaCl, KCl, NaI, etc. in aqueous solutions; in every case a pronounced negative slope in the mole-refraction-concentration curve is noticeable (*cf.* Geffcken. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, B, 5, 81). On the other hand, positive slopes in the curves are obtained with salts like $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, LiClO_4 , NaClO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , etc. In these cases it must be assumed that effects (ii) and (iv) preponderate over those of (i) and (iii). That is, either the anion is hydrated, which is less pronounced in the case of anions than cations, or there is a decreased dissociation of the salt. The second alternative seems more plausible.

In a previous paper (Majumdar and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*), it has been shown that although the alkali chlorides in aqueous solutions give a negative slope in the (R -conc.) curves, the same salts dissolved in borax glass reveal pronounced positive slopes. This points to a decreased dissociation of the salts in borax glass solvent (as opposed from dissociation in aqueous solution), as with a system like $\text{NaCl}-\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, the effect (iv), i.e. anion exchange with the solvent will have no significance. In the case of alkali sulphates on the other hand, the refractometric evidence reveals the existence of

undissociated molecules in concentrated aqueous solutions and the results recorded in the present paper show that in a glass medium the dissociation of the sulphates is still smaller. The result can also be expected from consideration of the low dielectric constant of the glass medium. This does not mean, however, that the electrical conductivity of these salts will be less in solution in glass than in the pure crystals. As a matter of fact we can conceive of a regular transition, so far as ionisation is concerned, from the crystal lattice to the aqueous solution, the state of solution in glass representing an intermediate stage. In one extreme we have the ions of the crystal held by strong electro-static forces, in the other, these forces are evanescent, while in solution in glass they exist in a subdued form.

The density of the dissolved salts is calculated from the additivity formula as follows :

$$d_{\text{mix}} = \frac{p \cdot d_1 + (100 - p) \cdot d_2}{100}$$

where d_{mix} is the calculated density of the mixture, p , the percentage of the salt, d_1 , the density of the pure salt and d_2 , the density of borax. The following values of density of fused $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, has been taken to be 2.356 and those of the salts are given in the respective tables.

TABLE VII
 Li_2SO_4 —borax system (d for $\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.221$)

Li_2SO_4	d obs.	d mix.
5.42%	2.3488	2.3486
8.52	2.3468	2.3444
11.45	2.3444	2.3405
13.23	2.3430	2.3381
14.80	2.3401	2.3364

TABLE VIII
 Na_2SO_4 —borax system. (d for $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.605$)

Na_2SO_4	d obs.	d mix.
5.87%	2.3719	2.3741
10.04	2.3821	2.3864
14.45	2.3951	2.4000
18.13	2.4042	2.4126
19.83	2.4072	2.4172

TABLE IX
 K_2SO_4 —borax system. (d for $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.665$)

K_2SO_4 %	d obs.	d mix.
5.91	2.3895	2.3723
11.16	2.3983	2.3900
17.64	2.4159	2.4104
19.50	2.4276	2.4162
21.56	2.4377	2.4226

Although the variation between the calculated and observed values of the densities of the mixtures are not very pronounced (less than 1% in the maximum deviation), the following regularities are, however, noticeable. In the cases of Li_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 , the observed values of density are slightly greater than the calculated values, while reverse is the case with Na_2SO_4 . The increase in the observed values in the two former cases seems to support the view of Zachariassen and Warren about the structure of boric oxide and borax glasses. According to these workers, an irregular or non-periodic three dimensional network is formed inside the glass with each boron atom linked with three others through an oxygen atom in each case. A structure like the above is thus formed within the glass. In the case of borax glass it is further assumed that the Na^+ ions are lodged inside the hollows of these three dimensional groupings. It may be conceived therefore that when a polar salt is dissolved in such a glass, its ions will penetrate inside the mesh and hence the observed density of the mixture will be greater than the value calculated from the additivity formula. The rival theory of crystallite formation in the glass would lead to a complete irregularity of mixing with consequent isotropy and one cannot expect any regularity in the variation of density between the observed and calculated values. Biltz who upholds the latter view has, however, explained the variation as due to the so-called "Packing effect" (Biltz, Weike and Schrader-Träger, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1937, 234, 282; *Glastech. Ber.*, 1938, 16, 131). The values of Na_2SO_4 , however, show a decrease in the observed value. This point is being further studied.

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